

In a Nutshell: Total Mixed Ration Silage

Dr. Pratik Joshi

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Animal Nutrition,
College of Veterinary Science & A.H., Kamdhenu University, Anand, Gujarat.

Total mixed rations (TMR) are produced by combining forages, by-products, concentrates, minerals, vitamins, and additives. Animals consume the nutrients required to meet the needs of maintenance and production from this mixture. Ensiling TMR is a long-established process. The ruminant production industry has shown a growing interest in TMR silage. The initial studies on TMR silage were published in the 1960s in the United States.

TMR silages have been shown to have a number of advantages, including the potential for incorporating unpalatable by-products (if their flavors and odors are altered by fermentation), the possibility of uniform composition during storage under farm conditions as well as high aerobic stability after feed out and a reduced requirement for labor and machinery (if TMR silage is purchased). TMR silages, like other silages, also have the potential to be commercialized, particularly if kept in smaller facilities (e.g., bales, bags, and pouches).

In the industry, TMR constituents are generally mixed in stationary mixer wagons and stored in big bags (e.g., 300 to 400 kg) or baled by agrarian compactors. The compactors are baler-wrapper combined machines suitable to pack the constituents by tying the bale with plastic film and further wrapping the pack with stretch plastic film. The resulting TMR bales have roughly high density 1000 kg of fresh matter, which has been associated with low nutrient loss during storage, even when the plastic film is damaged. These technologies allow for the flexible use of TMR silage by farmers and the transportation of the product. When the cost of TMR silage is reasonable, buying TMR silage in bags or bales can be a feasible option for small farmers without the resources to purchase equipment and feed storage facilities.

When TMR silage is made on a farm, it may be kept in several types of silos. To lessen the risk of aerobic deterioration during feed out, structures like ag-bags, pouches, drums, and bales are

preferable in small herds over bunkers or piles. For example, silage contractors in Italy are providing a customized service for baling, wrapping, and transporting 900–1200 kg TMR bales on farm.

By-products from the industrialization of cereal grains (including breweries and distilleries), soybean (including the biodiesel industry), sugarcane, cotton, peanut, cassava, vegetables, legumes, and fruits (including citrus growers and wineries) are among the valuable residues available in different regions. As a result, selling TMR silages that contain by-products has been an attractive commercial venture for the agricultural industry. TMR silage has also been suggested as a strategy to enhance the conservation of wet forages on small farms.

The nutritional composition of the diet can be modified when feeding a traditional TMR produced daily by adding alternative feedstuffs and supplements (such as sources of rumen undegraded protein (RUP) and vitamins) on top of conserved feeds (hays and whole-crop or grain silages). Contrarily, ensiling a TMR leads all nutrients to fermentation, which eventually changes the ration's feeding value by changing the content and availability of the nutrients.

Crops and by-products with high moisture content can be preserved using anaerobic storage techniques. Wet feedstuffs can avoid the energy costs of drying by ensiling rather than drying. Before ensiling, combining ingredients with different characteristics will enhance the conservation process. Ingredients that are dry and wet together may reduce the risk of unfavorable fermentation and effluent development. While materials that stimulate hetero-fermentation would increase the aerobic stability of TMR silages, ingredients rich in soluble sugars and homofermentative lactic acid bacteria would improve the fermentation.

